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WP2

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. Introduction	4
2. Objective and Scope	4
3. Statistics on WEEE Generation and Wastes potentially available for the Project.	6
3.1 Wastes from kitchen hobs. Estimation of potential waste arisings	6
3.2 Wastes from Ecolec Flows available for the Project.....	7
3.2.1 Wastes available for the Project resulting from ECOLEC flows	9
3.3 Prioritization of ECOLEC flows	12
4. Logistics Procedures: Transportation, handling and storage	13
4.1 WEEE Logistics Procedures	13
4.1.1 Handling	13
4.1.2 Storage.....	14
4.1.3 Transportation.....	14
4.2 Recovered components and materials Logistics Procedures	16
4.2.1 Reused components.....	16
4.2.2 Waste materials	16
5. Recoverability levels	17
6. Traceability of waste flows	17
6.1 Spanish official traceability system (Plataforma de Gestión de RAEE)	17
6.2 Traceability system implemented in the waste collection chain by ECOLEC	19
6.3 Traceability system at Preparing for Reuse Centers (CPRs)	19
6.3.1 Integration with Key Stakeholders ECOLEC and COPRECI Systems.....	20
7. Conclusions	21
Abbreviations and Acronyms	22
Referencias	22
Annex 1: Protocol for the selection and segregation of wastes from kitchen hobs	24
Annex 2: ECOLEC WEEE TRACKER Traceability System	26
Annex 3. Traceability Labels in Circular Replay System	30

1. Introduction

The LIFE WEELOOP project proposes a new holistic management system for Wastes from Electrical and Electronic Equipment (WEEE), based on circular economy models particularly focused on the recovery of materials and components of kitchen hobs (induction, radiant and hybrid) achieving a recovery rate of 90%.

The proper recycling of WEEE and the recovery of valuable components and materials is essential for both environmental protection and economic sustainability. Incorrect disposal of electronic waste can release harmful toxins into ecosystems, which poses significant risks to human health and biodiversity. Recovery and Recycling WEEE responsibly can help mitigate these dangers by conserving valuable resources and reducing the need for mining and raw material extraction. The LIFE WEELOOP project introduces innovative recovery processes, improving the efficiency of WEEE recycling by enabling the extraction of metals, plastics, and rare earth elements while minimizing energy consumption and waste production. These advancements not only enhance recycling outcomes but also contribute to a more sustainable waste management system.

In order to accomplish its objectives a key element is to define all process requirements which is addressed in Work Package WP2 “Requirements specifications & permits for process and industrialisation”. This Work Package includes specifically the Definition of Process Logistics and Supply that is addressed in this Deliverable D2.2. “Definition of process logistics and supply”.

Work package WP2 – Requirements specifications & permits for process and industrialisation

Work Package Number	WP2	Lead Beneficiary	2 - REPLAY
Work Package Name	Requirements specifications & permits for process and industrialisation		
Start Month	1	End Month	6

Objectives
<p>The aim of WP2 is the definition of all project requirements including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Definition of the process technical requirements for the development of the Circular AI platform. • Definition of process logistics and supply. • Definition of protocols for components and materials recovery. • Definition of technical specifications for recovered components and materials. • Definition of Digital Passport specifications for recovered components and materials and for the European Digital Product Passport for the new product. • Industrialisation requirements definition for the developed eco-designed product.

2. Objective and Scope

This Deliverable is connected to Task 2.3 that addresses the following points:

- WEEE generation at waste hubs: Relevant statistics on waste arisings generated based on public reports and quantities managed under the Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR)

systems, including generation by type of waste collector (quantities and quality). Quantification of WEEE collected that will be separated as an input for the recovery processes.

- WEEE logistics procedures´ definition and waste legal authorisations required.
- Means of collection necessary to store and transport products safely: containers design, specifications and supply.
- Traceability system, including the evaluation of the requirements for the integration of the platform of ECOLEC’s extended producer responsibility (EPR) scheme with Circular Replay´s.
- Assessment of recoverability potential of WEEE collected from segmented waste streams.

Therefore, its objective is to provide statistical data on waste generation, WEEE and waste hobs collected separately, define the logistics procedures and address the recoverability potential and describe the traceability systems to be put in place.

Deliverable D2.2 – Process logistics and supply definition

Deliverable Number	D2.2	Lead Beneficiary	5 - ECOLEC (EEAR)
Deliverable Name	Process logistics and supply definition		
Type	R — Document, report	Dissemination Level	PU - Public
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Description
Statistics, recoverability potential, quantification of the collected and separated WEEE, logistics procedures, transport and storage definition, and traceability. Electronic format. English.

Although this Deliverable includes a description to Legal Requirements, this aspect is described in more detail in the Deliverables 2.6 Legal Requirements that has also a Public character.

In any case, this Deliverable should be considered as a first version, since the level of understanding and control on the different topics will evolve during the Project. Therefore, this Deliverable may be subject to updates as significant developments arise.

Additionally, the scope of the data of waste hobs generation is shown to estimate the yearly production of this waste in Spain.

Calculations regarding the availability of wastes at the different waste hubs is limited to the flows directly managed by ECOLEC extended producer responsibility (EPR) scheme to address extended producer responsibilities for producers regarding the management of wastes from products they put on the market. ECOLEC EPR (or in Spanish SCRAP: sistema colectivo de responsabilidad ampliada del productor para RAEE) represents a 40 % in weight of the Category 4 large household appliances where the waste from kitchen hobs are included (MITECO, 2024). No consolidated data exist regarding the quantities of WEEE or waste hobs managed by the different EPRs in Spain or collected directly by the waste management companies and therefore, the total quantities could only be extrapolated based on ECOLEC’s market share and its management levels. In any case, since ECOLEC is the only EPR participating in WEELOOP Life Project and the only source of wastes so the perimeter of the scope for this deliverable is based on the flows directly controlled by ECOLEC as explained in Section 3.2.1.

3. Statistics on WEEE Generation and Wastes potentially available for the Project.

3.1 Wastes from kitchen hobs. Estimation of potential waste arisings

As shown in Table 1, according to market publications (ALIMARKET, 2021) the number of units of kitchen hobs put on the market in Spain during the 2016 – 2020 period were found between 900,000 and 1,100,000 units/year.

Reparto del mercado de electrodomésticos de línea blanca (SELL-IN) por familias (% Volumen)

Productos	2016	Cuota (%)	2017	Cuota (%)	2018	Cuota (%)	2019	Cuota (%)	2020	Cuota (%)
Lavadoras	1.714.000	25,9%	1.715.700	25,4%	1.750.000	24,60%	1.760.000	24,37 %	1.630.000	22,85 %
Frigoríficos	1.440.300	21,8%	1.463.600	21,6%	1.500.000	21,09%	1.540.000	21,33 %	1.550.000	21,73 %
Encimeras	938.500	14,2%	975.600	14,4%	1.070.000	15,04%	1.080.000	14,96 %	1.085.000	15,21 %
Campanas	759.800	11,5%	775.800	11,5%	840.000	11,81%	852.000	11,80 %	830.000	11,64 %
Lavavajillas	679.600	10,3%	713.100	10,5%	745.000	10,47%	760.000	10,52 %	775.000	10,87 %
Hornos	651.400	9,8%	686.500	10,2%	744.000	10,46%	760.000	10,52 %	780.000	10,94 %
Secadoras	224.800	3,4%	219.300	3,2%	250.000	3,51%	250.000	3,46 %	255.000	3,58 %
Congeladores	161.300	2,4%	150.100	2,2%	155.000	2,18%	160.000	2,22 %	180.000	2,52 %
Cocinas/Horno	47.800	0,7%	61.300	0,9%	59.000	0,83%	59.500	0,82 %	47.000	0,66 %
Total Línea Blanca	6.617.500	100,0%	6.761.000	100,0%	7.113.000	100,00%	7.221.500	100,00 %	7.132.000	100,00 %

Fuente: Elaboración con datos Anfel (sell-in), excepto 2018 y 2019, estimado por Alimarket.

Table 1: Estimation of quantities of products put on the market

Provided that

- (i) approximately 100,000 new homes were constructed annually in Spain in the same period (Ministerio de Transportes y Movilidad Sostenible, 2020),
- (ii) that according to market figures between 85 % and 90% of the market corresponds to repositions in a mature market and
- (iii) that the volume of the market shrank a 4% during the 2020-2024 period (APPLIA, 2025),

it can be estimated that the number of units of wastes from kitchen hobs disposed as wastes (waste arisings) are in the order of 900,000 units/year.

Based on the population of the different regions in Spain, the expected geographical distribution of waste arisings from kitchen hobs is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Expected geographical distribution by Region of kitchen hobs generation

3.2 Wastes from Ecolec Flows available for the Project

Table 2 shows the latest official figures available from EUROSTAT (EUROSTAT, 2024) on waste arisings from separate collection of household WEEE in Spain and also the quantities collected and managed under ECOLEC (ECOLEC, 2023) EPR system officially reported to the Spanish Government,

Household WEEE collected separately (tonnes)	2020	2021	2022
Spain total: Household wastes from Category 4 (FR4) Large equipment (EUROSTAT, 2024)	172,074	166,567	167,714
ECOLEC EPR: Household wastes from Category 4 (FR4) Large equipment (ECOLEC, 2021 -2024)	65,009	68,151	64,656
<i>% ECOLEC FR4 over total Spain FR4</i>	<i>38%</i>	<i>41%</i>	<i>39%</i>

Table 2: WEEE separately collected in Spain.

This table shows that ECOLEC scheme manages a percentage of all the wastes from the Category 4 similar to its 40% responsibility based on quantities of this Category of Products put on the market. Therefore, ECOLEC figures on WEEE Management on WEEE from Category 4 (or FR4) can be considered representative of the management at Spanish level and consequently be used for extrapolation purposes.

No specific figures exist at Spanish level on the specific waste management for kitchen hobs. However based on the actual figures of waste units managed by ECOLEC (ECOLEC, 2021 -2024), the average quantities of waste from kitchen hobs managed separately by EPR systems can be estimated in the order of 165,000 units/year (Table Table 3).

Household WEEE collected separately	2020	2021	2022	2023	Average (2020 – 2023)
ECOLEC: Waste from kitchen hobs managed (units) ¹	69,000	74,000	59,000	56,000	65,000
Total Spain: Waste hobs collected separately under EPR systems (units, estimated)	182,000	181,000	154,000	144,000	165,000

Table 3: Estimation of units of wastes from kitchen hobs separately collected.

The reduction in the quantities of wastes collected 2022 and 2023 is consistent with the reduction in the market of household appliances reported by APPLIA, the Association of manufacturers of domestic appliances. This reduction seems to have been stabilized in 2024 (APPLIA, 2025).

It should be highlighted that this estimate of 165,000 units/year of kitchen waste hobs currently collected greatly differ from initial estimations of approximately 900,000 units of waste hobs that may have been generated.

Actually, EUROSTAT waste management figures (EUROSTAT, 2024) based on EPRs reports to Public Authorities show a level of collection of approximately a 80% of the 65% POM₃ target for Category 4 (FR4) where the kitchen hobs are included, therefore approximately a 50% of the quantities put on the market.

Reasons for this divergence between units collected vs expected waste arisings need to be further investigated during the coming months in order to identify and address barriers, but could include among others (a.o.)

- Collection and Treatment of WEEE directly by authorized waste management companies outside the EPR systems (all-actors approach) and that are not reported using the correct codes according to LER-RAEE or EWC codes.
- Lack of discipline in the waste management chain to identify properly particular waste types, at product level, as it is not required by regulations,
- Impossibility to register specific waste types properly when they are collected in mixed containers with other WEEE from the same Category (e.g. at municipal collection points) and even that the collection, and
- Management of WEEE through non-controlled channels, either in metal scrap processing or illegally exported. As a reference The Global E-waste Monitor 2020 (UNITAR) quantified that roughly 40% to 45% of WEEE in Europe is handled outside the formal EPR systems

¹ Figures rounded to the nearest thousand

In order to increase the quantities of available wastes, the reasons for this significant gap between expected waste arisings and the waste hobs identified in the WEEE streams need to be further investigated and addressed during the remaining of the Project.

3.2.1 Wastes available for the Project resulting from ECOLEC flows

The figures of units of wastes from kitchen hobs as shown in Table , represent a best estimate of the total units identified in the WEEE flows reported. However, not all these wastes are necessarily available for the Project since a significant amount is collected by treatment operators for recycling at their facilities. It will be challenging to get access to these quantities and redirect these units to the Project. As an example some waste recyclers have stated that the transfer price to deliver their wastes hobs to the Project would be of between 8.00 and 10.00 €/unit in order to cover the costs of access to waste, collection, sorting, transportation and profit losses from selling the materials recovered from recycling operations.

As a result of the above, ECOLEC initially focuses on the quantities collected by logistic operators that are independent from recycling waste management companies to be provided to Life WEEELOOP Project. These controlled flows by the ECOLEC represent a 50% of the total number of units of wastes shown in Table , and therefore in the order of 30,000 units/year.

This is the baseline, so that additional efforts will have to be made to identify new collection points, sources of wastes and actors to involve in order to increase progressively these quantities. Moreover, specific collection means, logistic protocols and procedures, as well as surveillance and legislative enforcement will be necessary to ensure that reusable products are derived from the collection points to preparing for reuse instead of to recycling processes to comply with the waste management hierarchy and WEEE Spanish regulation.

In order to prioritize activities it is also important to be able to segregate the flows of wastes available for the Project based on the (i) their geographical origins and (ii) type of origins.

3.2.1.1 Distribution by Geographical Origin

Based on ECOLEC reports, the distribution in percentage of the quantities of wastes collected by independent logistic operators for ECOLEC during the 2020 – 2024 period are shown in Figure 2. This shows that the Regions with the higher percentages in quantities collected by ECOLEC are not aligned with either the expected generation levels shown in Figure 1: Expected geographical distribution by Region of kitchen hobs generation Figure 1, or with the locations where the two Preparing for Reuse Centers (in Spanish, Centros de Preparación para la Reutilización or CPRs) are located, EMAÚS in the Basque Region and ÉXXITA in Andalusia.

Figure 2: Distribution (in %) of the separately collected wastes from kitchen hobs by ECOLEC based on geographical origin

Collected wastes are in general consolidated at interim storage facilities (in Spanish, Centros de Almacenamiento Temporal) acting as logistic hubs (or nodes) where the wastes from kitchen hobs may be classified, segregated, stored separately and shipped. The distribution of wastes stored by ECOLEC logistics operators at major consolidation hubs is shown in Figure .

Figure 3: Distribution of quantities of wastes from kitchen hobs available at waste hubs.

3.2.1.2 Distribution per type of origin

In general, the types of origin of the wastes from kitchen hobs collected by ECOLEC EPR can be categorized in three types:

- Retailers, both large and small.
- EEE producers’ networks, resulting from their reverse logistic flows or repair services
- Municipal collection points.

Figure 2 below shows that 87% of the waste collected and controlled by ECOLEC comes from the retail sector while 9% are collected from municipal collection points and 4 % are generated at the networks established by EEE producers.

Figure 2: Distribution (in %) of the separately collected wastes from kitchen hobs by ECOLEC based on types of origin

The differentiation by type of origin is important because the conditions of the collected waste vary depending on the origin due to handling and storage means and practices. While waste collected from retailers or from EEE producers are, in general, stored individually at municipal collection points they may be stored in containers mixed with other wastes from the same fraction FR4. As a result of the later, wastes from municipal collection points are often broken (Figure 3) or even scavenged and therefore are more difficult to be segregated at interim collection facilities in good conditions to be subject to Preparing for Reuse (PxR) operations.

Figure 3: Example of a kitchen hob waste broken

3.3 Prioritization of ECOLEC flows

As a result of the analysis performed, it was decided to prioritize in this first period (M01 – M06) the segregation and shipment of separated collected hob wastes from hubs based on the following criteria:

1. Proximity to the Preparing for Reuse Centers (In Spanish, Centros de Preparación para la Reutilización or CPRs).
2. Level of integration in ECOLEC reverse logistics and waste management chain, which affects to the willingness to cooperate and adherence to ECOLEC traceability and labeling procedures.
3. Expected conditions of the wastes collected.

As shown in Table 3: Waste consolidation nodes activated during the first 6 months of WEELOOP Project, seven logistic nodes operated by four logistic operators that consolidate wastes from four Regions (Comunidades Autónomas) have been activated during this first period of the Project (M01-M03). Pending of the final figures, it is estimated that between 1,300 and 1,500 units have been directed to the two CPRs participating in the Project. However, the great majority of these units, a 86% of them, were received by the CPR in the Basque Country, which is somehow consistent with the management levels by ECOLEC at the activated nodes (Figure 2).

CPR ÉXXITA (Andalusia)	CPR EMAÚS (Basque Country)
3 nodes (1 Region) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Waste Hub OL #1 Huelva ❖ Waste Hub OL#2 Seville ❖ Waste Hub OL#2 Málaga 	4 nodes (3 Regions) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Emaús (consortium member) ❖ Waste Hub OL #2 Bizkaia (incl. Cantabria) ❖ Waste Hub OL #3 Bizkaia ❖ Waste Hub OL #4 Baleares

Table 3: Waste consolidation nodes activated during the first 6 months of WEELOOP Project

Main learnings from the experience so far are as follows:

- Significant effort required to instruct waste management operators in the proper selection and transportation of wastes.
- High importance of the proper selection of wastes suitable for PxR Operations. As a result of it, CIRCULAR REPLAY developed a first set of requirements that is included as Annex 1.
- Importance of handling, containerization and stowage procedures to maximize the PxR recovery potential and the safety of personnel involved in the management.
- Difficulties to get the support of Logistic Operators to ship wastes to the CPR in Seville due to the lack of routes.
- Importance of the participation and involvement of all the actors in the Consortium to activate new collection centers, logistic nodes and public and private waste managers in order to increase waste hobs collected and derived to CPRs.
- Specific means should be deployed and proper selection procedures implemented at municipal collection points in order to improve the segregation and quality of the collected waste hobs.

4. Logistics Procedures: Transportation, handling and storage

4.1 WEEE Logistics Procedures

As a starting point, logistics operations shall only be performed by authorized transport and/or by waste management companies and in compliance with regulatory requirements for the handling, storage and transportation of wastes described in Section 3.5 End-of-life Management, Collection and Treatment Requirements of Project Deliverable 2.6 “Legal Requirements”. Furthermore, these operations should be carried out in accordance with these legal requirements, as well as in full compliance with the provisions of their permits.

Moreover, to ensure both safe and environmentally sound practices while achieving the objectives of the WEELOOP project, the following procedures shall be implemented.

4.1.1 Handling

- WEEE must be handled, stored, and transported in a way that prevents environmental contamination, physical damage, and health risks.
- WEEE must be handled, stored, and transported in a way that prevents environmental contamination, physical damage, and health risks.
- Preliminary Assessment and Selection: Upon collection, WEEE should be promptly inspected to determine its suitability for reuse according to the criteria established Annex 1: Protocol for the selection and segregation of wastes from kitchen hobs.
- Segregated units should be labeled and operations registered in compliance with the legal requirements and with the EPR procedures as described in Section 7. Traceability of waste flows and in Annex 2: ECOLEC WEEE TRACKER Traceability System.
- Protection Measures: To prevent damage and preserve the integrity of the waste hobs, items should be covered during storage and transportation. Additionally, they should be either properly wrapped or put inside pallet boxes as the cardboard boxes that ECOLEC can provide to members of the Project in order to ensure a proper stowage conditions during transportation (Figure 4). These boxes are made of cardboard quality K4/3F/K4, wave BC and their dimensions are 1,184 mm x 790 mm x 980 mm. These cardboard oxes can be supplied under these specifications by different manufacturers such as ECOBOX, DS SMITH o CARTOSPÉ.

Figure 4: ECOLEC pallet cardboard box suitable for the handling and transportation of waste hobs

- Personnel involved in the collection and handling of WEEE should receive appropriate training to identify non-hazardous items and handle them in a manner that preserves their potential for reuse. This includes understanding the importance of segregation and proper storage.

4.1.2 Storage

- Storage areas must be well-ventilated, secure, and protected from weather conditions.
- All WEEE must be stored in weatherproof conditions to prevent water infiltration and exposure to environmental factors. and over an impermeable flooring to contain spills.
- Storage facilities will provide spaces and means for separate collection of WEEE that may be destined for preparing for reuse,
- Separate storage areas for different WEEE categories will be identified and marked with the WEEE to be stored, including its denomination and LER-RAEE codes.

4.1.3 Transportation

- Documentation: Any operation of transport should comply with all documentation requirements such as Document of Acceptance (Treatment Contract in Spanish) and Identification Document (Documento de Identificación in Spanish). This documentation will include EWC (LER-RAEE) codes, quantities, identification of origin and destination facilities, identification of treatment method at destination facility and contact information for the transporter. Upon delivery, the recipient facility shall verify and sign the Identification

Document, confirming receipt and acceptance of the waste. All parties involved—producer, transporter, and recipient—must retain copies of this document for at least three (3) years. These documents must be processed electronically through e-SIR electronic platform developed by Spanish Ministry for the Environmental Transition (MITECO) and in some cases like in Andalusia through the similar platforms established by some Regional Governments (Comunidades Autónomas).

- o Vehicles should be authorized for the transportation of the wastes, be properly ensured and undergo regular inspections to verify compliance.
- o Stowage: WEEE transported shall be secured to prevent movement during transit, thereby ensuring the safety of the driver, vehicle, and other road users. Proper stowage should prevent the load from sliding, tilting, swaying, deforming, or rotating. To achieve this, methods such as blocking, locking, or lashing are employed, often in combination. If these methods are not implemented the load could move and present risks during transportation or unloading operations as shown in **¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia..**

Figure 5: Example of waste conditions resulting from an improper stowage

Compliance with these requirements and with ECOLEC's internal protocols - including the traceability system - will be evaluated by ECOLEC as part of its certified ISO 9001:2015 Quality and ISO 14001:2015 Environmental Management systems. Additionally, it is recommended that the specific elements of the CENELEC or UNE-EN 50625-4 Standard on Collection and Logistics Requirements are also adopted by waste management companies performing these operations.

4.2 Recovered components and materials Logistics Procedures

4.2.1 Reused components

Once the preparing for reuse treatment is completed, the components recovered are no longer waste and become recovered components according to Royal Decree 110/2015, on WEEE.

The components initially foreseen subject to recovery for reuse in the kitchen hobs industry are:

- Ceramic glass plates
- PCB
- Induction coils.

Specific containers and packaging for recovered components will be used to ensure safety during handling, storage, loading, transport and unloading at destiny.

Each container will include identification of the origin (shipping address), destination and will include a packing list so that each recovered component can be traced.

Transport of these products will comply with the Spanish legislation, for the transport of goods which establishes key requirements that will be deployed to ensure the safety of the means of transport and transport vehicle, minimize risks and ensure safety on the road for both carriers and other road users:

- Load securing: the load will be well distributed and secured to prevent shifting, falling or tipping during transport. Tie-downs, anchorages and other suitable fastening systems must be used.
- Condition and maintenance of vehicles: Trucks and other transport vehicles will comply with periodic technical inspections and be in good working order, with special attention to brakes, tires, lights and suspension.
- Weight and dimensions: Weight and dimension limits established by regulations will be respected to avoid overloads that could compromise road safety and vehicle stability.
- Adequate signage: Vehicles transporting dangerous or oversized goods will have special signage (plates, lights and badges) to alert other drivers and ensure safe transport.
- Driver training: Carriers will be adequately trained and respect driving and resting times to avoid fatigue.

4.2.2 Waste materials

The materials extracted during the preparing for reuse process are considered waste, unless the end of waste status is reached.

These waste materials are:

- Ceramic glass cullets*
- Plastics: ABS, polypropylene...
- Ferrous metals: iron and steel.
- Non-ferrous metals: copper and aluminum.
- PCBs: printed circuit boards non reusable.
- Wiring

* A specific recovery treatment process has been designed by Circular Replay and Copreci to be implemented in the CPR to recover this material. The aim is to complying with the technical industry specifications so that it can be supplied as secondary material to be consumed in the hobs

manufacturing industry. Provided that the end-of-waste status criteria for the glass cullets recovered from hobs is not regulated yet, either at European or National level, the necessary Authorisation from the Regional Administration where the CPR is located must be obtained.

Each material type will be stored in specific containers and packaging will be used to ensure safety and that they are protected during storage and loading in the CPR, during transport and during unloading at the clients' premises.

Each container will be identified with a label that will comply with the provisions of Article 21 of La2 7/2022, on Waste, such as the Unique European Waste Code - LER Code, Description of the waste, Center of origin and Date of entry.

Transport of these waste materials to be recycled will comply with the requirements established in the waste legislation described in section 3.5. of the Deliverable D2.6., on Legal Requirements.

5. Recoverability levels

The effective levels of recoverability through preparing for reuse (PxR) achieved so far by the CPRs are around 8% to 9% by weight of the waste managed. The main reason is that PxR efforts have primarily focused on the recovery and reuse of glass tops. Furthermore, some shipments have arrived with significant surface damage due to the condition of the waste at collection points or issues during transportation.

As additional components and materials are targeted for PxR (e.g., certain types of induction hobs), conditions at collection points improve, and proper storage and containerization of transported devices are enhanced, it is expected that PxR levels will exceed 15% by weight of the waste managed by CPRs.

Furthermore, the overall preparing for reuse and recycling levels achieved for the waste hobs managed—whether at the CPRs or at the waste recycling facilities where the resulting material waste was shipped—are approximately 86%, well above the minimum 80% target set at the EU or Spain level for this waste category.

6. Traceability of waste flows

Traceability system being put in place for the Project needs to meet both the applicable regulatory requirements and also the needs of the participants in the Project. Although they are different in focus and in purpose, it is planned to maximize their integration in order to avoid multiple unconnected systems.

6.1 Spanish official traceability system (Plataforma de Gestión de RAEE)

Spanish Royal Decree 110/2015 (MITECO, RD 110/2015), contemplates the need to register all waste management operations in a common electronic platform for the management of WEEE (or Plataforma electrónica de gestión de RAEE in Spanish). This electronic WEEE management platform (MITECO, 2018) was further developed in Ministerial Order TED/1032/2024 (MITECO, 2024) that established the obligation of registering WEEE Management operations and entered into force on 2

January 2025 (although the electronic ICT platform actually entered into operation effectively on 2 February 2025)

In line with the principles of administrative simplification and telematic processing in public administrations, this platform is intended to act as a single database on the collection and treatment of waste electrical and electronic equipment (WEEE) and will be fed by the operators who collect or receive WEEE for the first time and by the managers who treat it. This should guarantee the control and traceability of WEEE, since the platform will be the means through which managers comply with their information obligations such as maintaining the chronological file and the annual report.

The electronic WEEE management ICT platform will collect information on the collection and management of WEEE in each autonomous community and at the national level. The use of a single platform should create a single source of WEEE collection and management data, and avoid certain distortions generated by the multiplicity of platforms. Likewise, it should facilitate the control surveillance of WEEE data and its management by public administrations.

A particular feature of the traceability system established by the WEEE management ICT platform is the obligation to tag the WEEE with labels that allow its electronic reading (QR code). These labels (Figure 6) are generated directly by the ICT platform although it is expected and desirable its compatibility with existing systems that some EPR schemes have already in place.

Figure 6: Example of the label issued by the Spanish ICT traceability platform (Plataforma de Gestión de RAEE)

This Ministerial Order defines deadlines for Individual Labeling of WEEE by collection Category. For the wastes from Category 4 where the wastes from kitchen hobs are included, it defines the following timeframes:

- Collective labeling during the first two years from the Order's effective date (until 1 January 2027)
- Individual labeling obligation will apply from the second year after the order entered into force, therefore from 2 January 2027. However, voluntary individual labeling may be implemented voluntarily from the date of entry into force.

From the date of entry into force of this Order, the different operators are required to join progressively the electronic platform according to this calendar:

- WEEE waste management companies and preparing-for-reuse centers: From the date of entry into force (January 2025), although the electronic ICT platform entered effectively in operation on 3 February 2025)
- Distributors of EEE: Within six months after the order enters into force (by 2 July 2025).

- Local entities: Within six months after the order enters into force, ensuring that their collection facilities comply with the requirements (by 2 July 2025).

Although waste management operators shall comply with the requirements of the Official ICT Platform for the management of WEEE, it is a common understanding that it will allow its compatibility with the systems developed by some management operators and EPRs that are already in place, as the one already put in place by ECOLEC that is described in Section **¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.**

6.2 Traceability system implemented in the waste collection chain by ECOLEC

ECOLEC has in place a traceability system called WEEE TRACKER that is based on labels with a QR and barcode as those shown in Figure 7. The system allows the traceability of labeled wastes at unit level from the first collection until the final treatment capturing information on waste types, timings, operations performed, weights, incidences, etc. This system is connected to ECOLEC ECOAPP ICT system and requires the use of PDAs and labels that are provided by ECOLEC to its waste management chain and therefore to the ÉXXITA and EMAÚs in the consortium that are using the system already. A general description of the system is provided in Annex 2.

Figure 7: Examples of labels used in ECOLEC's WEEE TRACKER traceability system

The features, characteristics and integration protocols were shared with CIRCULAR REPLAY in M03 in order to facilitate the integration of the different ICT systems used in the Project. Version 2 of ECOAPP is planned to be deployed starting from M07 with the aim to make it compatible during 2025 with the requirements of the official ICT Platform of the Spanish Ministry for the Ecological Transition described in Section 6.1 that entered in operation in February 2025 (M05 of the Project).

6.3 Traceability system at Preparing for Reuse Centers (CPRs)

The hobs recovery process involves several stages to ensure efficient handling, traceability, and compliance with legal and environmental standards. The process takes place at designated Hob Recovery Centers, also known as Nodes.

Circular Replay has a traceability system to assist and trace these processes: developed to close the loop, document and certify the circular origin of components and materials recovered from waste, reintroduced in the appliances industry:

- **New Reception Process:** The process begins with the registration of incoming shipments from Extended Producer Responsibility Systems (SCRAP). The batches containing the hobs are weighed, labeled, and tracked to ensure proper documentation and traceability. This step ensures that the hobs are prepared for subsequent treatment and recycling stages.
- **Check-In Process:** Each hob is individually identified, weighed, and recorded in the Circular Replay's proprietary system (CRIA). The system ensures accurate tracking of each hob's characteristics, and the hobs are labeled for easy tracking throughout the process. They are then temporarily stored until they move on to the dismantling process.
- **Entry Certification:** An external agent certifies the incoming hobs to verify that they meet regulatory requirements for processing. This certification ensures transparency and traceability, confirming the materials adhere to the necessary standards for the recovery process.
- **Treatment Process:** The hobs are dismantled on a specialized worktable, with guidance from the CRIA system. This system identifies reusable components (such as heating elements, control panels, and ceramic glass) and flags them for recovery. Operators verify the physical and functional condition of the components, deciding whether they should be reused or recycled.
- **Treatment Certification:** After dismantling, a treatment certification is issued, documenting the quantity of material recycled and reused. This certification ensures that the process complies with regulatory standards and that the mass balance of recovered materials is correct. It also confirms that the treatment was conducted in an environmentally responsible manner, ensuring the recovery process aligns with sustainability goals. For further information about this process, please see section 6 in document 2.1 Requirements Specifications & Permits for Process and Industrialization .

For further information about this process, please see Annex 3. Traceability Labels in Circular Replay System and section 6 in document 2.1 Requirements Specifications & Permits for Process and Industrialization.

6.3.1 Integration with Key Stakeholders ECOLEC and COPRECI Systems

Effective collaboration among manufacturers, recyclers, repair centers, and other stakeholders will be essential for the success of the circular economy. The Circular AI Platform will facilitate this collaboration by integrating with stakeholders' existing systems, enabling real-time data exchange and coordinated operations across the value chain.

For instance, integration with a recycler's traceability platform will allow for continuous data sharing, ensuring that materials are tracked and handled according to environmental and regulatory standards. This real-time data exchange will improve the accuracy of material sorting, recovery, and reporting, enhancing the efficiency of recycling operations. Additionally, connecting with a manufacturer's Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) system will enable the platform to track recovered components in real-time, allowing them to be efficiently reintegrated into remanufacturing workflows. This integration will provide manufacturers with visibility into the status of recovered materials, ensuring that components meet the necessary specifications for reuse in new products. By integrating key systems across the value chain, the Circular AI Platform will foster collaboration among stakeholders,

driving efficiency and sustainability in the recovery process and ensuring alignment with circular economy principles.

7. Conclusions

In order to ensure sufficient quantities of waste hobs suitable for the Preparing for Reuse pursued, an assessment of the current and foreseen waste arisings were performed. A significant gap has been detected between the quantities of wastes initially expected and those identified in the waste flows managed by the extended producer responsibility schemes. Although some reasons for the gap have been identified, this should be further investigated and addressed in order to increase available quantities.

During this first period of WEELOOP Project (M01-M06), waste logistic nodes have been activated based on principles of proximity and suitability. However, due to the availability of waste hobs in ECOLEC managed network, a lack of balance was detected since most of the wastes (86% approximately) were found in the area of influence of the CPR of EMAÚS in the Basque Region.

Plan is in place to activate more waste nodes and ship additional quantities of waste hobs from ECOLEC network to the CPRs. However, this will require an increase in transportation distances and the engagement of logistic operators who may have to modify existing operational practices and transport routes.

In order to foster the application of the waste management hierarchy and increase the quantities and the quality of the wastes arriving to the current preparing for reuse centers, segregation of waste hobs at collection points, both municipal and retail, will be assessed with the purpose of diverting these flows directly to the CPRs or to the logistic waste nodes.

Although the conditions of the wastes collected at the municipal collection point tested were found to be deficient, it should be assessed the identification of other centers with large production of waste hobs, adequate segregation means, surveillance and antirobbery conditions, as well as the possibility of improving them by implementing specific separate collection means and procedures to segregate kitchen hobs and maintain their integrity so that they are suitable for PxR at CPRs.

Additionally, it seems necessary to assess the possibility of expanding the network of CPRs is extended to provide a better geographical coverage. This would not only reduce transportation costs and distances – and therefore carbon footprint - but would also greatly facilitate the logistics operations and the engagement of logistic operators.

Furthermore, efforts should be made to incorporate flows from other sources – including other EPR systems besides ECOLEC – and to segregate waste hobs at recycling facilities.

Further to the quantities, the conditions of the collected wastes have been identified as a potential issue for their recoverability in CPRs. Therefore, procedures have been implemented to select and segregate these waste units with the highest potential for recoverability of materials and/or components. Additionally, efforts are required to implement the logistic procedures defined to optimize the conditions for the recovery at CPRs and ensure compliance with legal requirements and the safety of the employees involved in the waste management operations.

Preparing for Reuse recoverability levels during the first period reached a 9% by weight of the wastes managed at CPRs which contributes to achieve the PxR 4% minimum target for Category 4. It is foreseen that a proper selection of the wastes at collection facilities, the implementation of the logistics procedures and the extension of components suitable for PxR will significantly increase these levels. In any case, the 86% PxR and recycling level achieved exceeds the 80% minimum target established by legislation.

Abbreviations and Acronyms

AI: Artificial Intelligence

CPR: Centro de Preparación para la Reutilización (in English Preparing for Reuse Center)

EPR: Extended Producer Responsibility systems for waste flows.

ERP: Enterprise Resource Planning system

EWC: European Waste Code

FR: Fraction of Wastes as detailed in Table 1 of Spanish RD 110/2015 on WEEE.

ICT: Information and Communication Technologies based system

ISO: International Standard Organizations

INTERPOL: International Criminal Police Organization.

LER-RAEE: Lista Europea de Residuos adapted for WEEE

POM₋₃: Average of quantities in weight put on the market during the past three years.

PDA: Personal Digital Assistant allowing to read tags (barcodes or QR)

PxR: Preparing for Reuse.

RD: (Spanish) Royal Decree.

QR: Quick-Response code consisting of an array of black and white squares, typically used for storing URLs or other information for reading by the camera on a smartphone.

UNU: United Nations University, now UNITAR: United Nations Institute for Training and Research.

WEEE: Waste from electrical and electronic equipment

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Annex I: Protocol for the selection and segregation of wastes from kitchen hobs

GUÍA INDICATIVA DE LOS RESIDUOS DE ENCIMERAS A ENVIAR A CPR-ESPECIALIZADOS PARA LA RECUPERACIÓN DE COMPONENTES PARA SU REUTILIZACIÓN

Se muestra, a título ilustrativo, una lista no exhaustiva con ejemplos que ayudan a identificar las encimeras solicitadas para su envío a CPR especializados.

El objetivo es evitar el envío de residuos no solicitados, que puedan producir riesgos a los trabajadores que intervienen en los procesos o ineficiencias en el sistema.

Si el centro de recogida tiene dudas sobre la idoneidad de su envío al CPR especializado, el residuo se destinará a planta de tratamiento para su descontaminación y reciclaje.

Ejemplos de residuos solicitados para su envío a CPR Especializado

Descripción	Ejemplo	Foto ilustrativa
Encimeras de inducción y radiantes	Paletización retractilado/flejado	
Encimeras de inducción	Con cristal negro, focos de inducción	
Encimeras vitrocerámicas radiantes	Con cristal negro, focos radiantes	
Encimeras con daños superficiales	Con cristal arañado/con leves roturas	

circular replay[®]

Ejemplos de residuos **NO solicitados** para su envío a CPR Especializado

Descripción	Ejemplo	Foto ilustrativa
Residuo impropio (No es encimera)	Hornos	
Residuo no gestionable (restos de encimeras)	Encimera con fragmentos de cristal roto que pueda generar riesgos a los operarios del CPR.	
Residuo no gestionable (restos de encimeras)	Conjunto vidrio de encimera sin elementos recuperables para su reutilización	
Encimeras de gas	Cocina de gas con quemadores (versión blanca)	
Encimeras de gas	Cocina de gas con quemadores (versión negra)	
Encimeras de inducción con cristal blanco (muy poco habitual)	Encimera con cristal blanco	

Annex 2: ECOLEC WEEE TRACKER Traceability System

MANUAL FUNCIONAMIENTO WEEE TRACKER

CONECTA CON EL RECICLAJE RESPONSABLE

1. INICIO APLICACIÓN

Pantalla de acceso

Pantalla principal

2. NUEVA RECOGIDA

Paso 3

NUEVA RECOGIDA 3 - RAEE: Listado RAEE

3 Etiqueta(s) Leida(s)

Etiqueta	Canib	R. Especifico	Cont
18410708200877291	No	--	--
18410708200877292	No	--	--
18410708200877293	No	--	--

BORRAR MOD.RAEE

AÑADIR MÁS RAEEs

NUEVA RECOGIDA 3 - RAEE: Editar RAEE

Etiqueta: 18410708200877291

Fracción: Residuo:

Sel. Fra. Selecciona Residuo

Residuo Especifico: Selecciona R. Especifico

Marca: Campo no obligatorio

Tipo Contenedor: Selecciona Tipo Contenedor

Canibalizado:

NUEVA RECOGIDA 3 - RAEE: Editar RAEE

Etiqueta: 18410708200877291

Fracción: Residuo:

FR1 DOMESTICO - FRIGORIFICO...

Residuo Especifico: FRIGORIFICO

Marca: Campo no obligatorio

Tipo Contenedor: Unidades sueltas

Canibalizado:

NUEVA RECOGIDA 3 - RAEE: Listado RAEE

3 Etiqueta(s) Leida(s)

Etiqueta	Canib	R. Especifico	Cont
18410708200877291	No	FRIGORIFICO	Unidades sueltas
18410708200877292	No	FRIGORIFICO	Unidades sueltas
18410708200877293	No	LAVADORAS	Unidades sueltas

BORRAR MOD.RAEE

AÑADIR MÁS RAEEs

3. NUEVA ENTREGA

Paso 3

NUEVA ENTREGA 3 - RAEE: Nuevo RAEE

Etiqueta: 18410708200877291

Fracción: Residuo:

FR1 DOMESTICO - FRIGORIFICO...

Residuo Especifico: FRIGORIFICO

Marca: Campo no obligatorio

Tipo Contenedor: Unidades sueltas

Canibalizado:

Reciclaje: Reutilización:

NUEVA ENTREGA 3 - RAEE: Listado RAEE

1 Etiqueta(s) Leida(s)

Etiqueta	Canib	R. Especifico	Cont
18410708200877291	No	FRIGORIFICO	Unidades sueltas

AÑADIR MÁS RAEEs

5. NUEVA RECEPCIÓN – Recepción Gestores ECOLEC

Paso 2

6. CONSULTAR STOCK

FRACCIÓN	UNIDADES
FR1	11
FR4	4
FR5	4

VER RESUMEN INDIVIDUAL

8. OPERATIVAS REALIZADAS

C/Doctor Fleming, 51. 28036 Madrid. España

ecolec.es

Teléfono: 91 831 01 83

ecolec@ecoles.es

#ConectaConElReciclajeResponsable

Annex 3. Traceability Labels in Circular Replay System

CR-IA:
Process assistant and Traceability platform for Preparing for Reuse in WEEELoop model

Powered by

Batches Labels in New reception process each label contains the logo of the node it belongs to.

<p>ET/E: DCS30482021731520250774428 Origen: LOGIRAEES SL NIMA: 4820217315 RAEE / FR4 Código LER: 200136-42</p>	1
<p style="text-align: right; margin: 0;">26/02/2025 10:21:2 Num. 33 GRAM PRECISION Xtrem s/n - 279.00 Kg</p>	

<p>ET/E: DCS30410001700320247723135(1) Origen: LOGIRAEES SL NIMA: 2147483647 RAEE / FR4 Código LER: 200136-42</p>	1
<p style="text-align: right; margin: 0;">26/02/2025 10:18:5 Num. 28 GRAM PRECISION Xtrem s/n - 136.00 Kg</p>	

Individual label for each hob.in the Check In Process

Registro de entrada
20-02-2025 13:18

11.955 Kg

Bulto: DCS30482021731520250774428/1	
Ticket: 1612580	Marca: BOSCH
Modelo: PIE665E	PN: PIE665E/01
Nº Serie: 103FD8307024893	
RAEE/FR4 200136-42	
Origen: LOGIRAEES SL	
NIMA: 4820217315	

Digital passport label carried by each recovered component to ensure its individual traceability.

Label used to close the batch of components ready to be sold, containing the origin information of each component from its entry to the node. With the integration of the SCRAP platforms, traceability from the collection point can also be incorporated.

Cierre de Caja

21-08-2024 11:09

12.000 Kg

Caja N°: CJXX-XXXXXX
Tipo:
Código LER:
RAEE/FR4 200136-42
Modelo:
Origen:
NIMA: